

THEORITICAL AND NUMERICAL ANALYSES OF LAMINATED FIBROUS COMPOSITE E-SPRINGS FOR VEHICLE SUSPENSION SYSTEMS

Salah A. Elmoselhy*, Badr S. Azzam**, and Sayed M. Metwalli***

M. S. Candidate, **Assist. Prof., *Prof. and Head*

Mech. Design and Prod. Dept, Faculty of Engineering, Cairo University, Egypt

elmoselhy@netscape.net, badr_azzam@hotmail.com, and pantech@idsc.net.eg

ABSTRACT: An optimized trend of springs in automotive suspension systems is introduced. Such springs are called “Laminated Fibrous Composite E-springs”. They can efficiently replace the traditional coil or multi-leaf springs. E-springs are composed of laminated composites of extremely high structural strength and stiffness to weight ratios. Furthermore, E-springs require reduced space rather than the traditional multi-leaf springs. These features can result in a considerable reduction in weight, and consequently greater efficiency and energy saving. A comparison of diversified configurations of springs is performed using a theoretical analysis of stresses and deflections. The theoretical results are then verified numerically through a finite element analysis technique. Results of the theoretical analysis show a well agreement with the numerical results. The comparison of the diversified configurations concludes that the highest deflection and almost the same level of induced stresses are for a special E-configuration. Results show that the special E-configuration could be adopted as a good configuration. The geometrical parameters of the E-spring are optimized and the static stiffness is also investigated numerically.

KEY WORDS: Composite Springs, Finite Element Analysis, Vehicle Suspension

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last ten years, revolutions in software, materials, manufacturing, and other techniques had made it possible to design an automobile that surpasses ordinary vehicle’s limitations. The idea of using hybrid composite materials in the springs of automotive suspension systems reflects an innovation in a long string of automotive innovations. Spring design involves the relationship between force, torque, deflection, and resulted stresses. Springs have many duties in connection with the entire structure of the vehicle: to cushion impact and shock loading, and to allow the wheel to follow the irregular contour of the road surface. Weight savings on specific components such as composite leaf springs can exceed 70 percent compared with steel ones (composite leaf springs have also proved to be more fatigue resistant than steel springs) [9]. Composites generally have better damping than conventional metallic structural materials, especially if the composite has one or more polymeric constituents [9]. Hybrid composite materials have unique features that can be used to meet diverse and competing design requirements in a more cost-effective way than either advanced or conventional composites. Hybrids give designers the opportunity to achieve weight saving, enhanced performance, and simpler designs with minimal use of higher-performance reinforcement. Some of the specific advantages of hybrids over conventional composites are balanced strength and stiffness, balanced bending and membrane mechanical properties, balanced thermal-distortion stability, reduced weight and/or cost, improved fatigue resistance, reduced notch sensitivity, improved fracture toughness and/or crack-arresting properties, and improved impact resistance.

Originally, Sancaktar [1] designed a composite leaf spring for light vehicle applications. In such research work, the solar car’s front suspension leaf spring was redesigned. He concluded that redesigning, analysis, and optimization of composite leaf springs were performed successfully. More recently, Sardou [2] developed a composite compression C-springs for vehicle suspension. In his research work, Sardou compared composite C-springs with traditional metallic multi-leaf springs. He concluded that C-springs considerably surpassed the traditional metallic multi-leaf springs in avoiding delamination of leaves, light weight, simple fixation, reduced cost, improved fatigue life, and non-linear spring rate stiffness. Lately, Azzam et.al [3] have performed theoretical and numerical

analyses of fibrous composite C-springs. Such research work has comprised a theoretical analysis of composite springs followed by a finite element analysis. Some numerical models were built, which have different configurations of lay-ups, and different fibrous materials to optimize the effects of these parameters on the behavior of C-springs in the numerical analysis. The analysis has included the whole steel, laminated steel, and laminated composite springs. It was concluded that a good agreement was obtained between the numerical and theoretical analyses. Therefore composite materials have showed well behavior as substituting materials for steel in manufacturing of C-springs. In the current work, in an endeavor to make a conceptual design of an optimized spring for the front-suspension of a vehicle, diversified materials and configurations of springs are compared, and the best of them is optimized.

2. THEORETICAL DEFLECTION AND STRESS ANALYSES

Deflection and stress could be considered among the primary measures for assessing elastic mechanical element alternatives. Steel traditional multi-leaf spring as shown in Fig. 1, steel E-spring as shown in Fig. 2-i, and steel C-spring as shown in Fig. 3-i, are compared theoretically regarding their maximum deflection and maximum induced stress. They all have the same material (steel AISI 9255 Alloy steel) [4,5], and subjected to the same applied load (555 kg, Quarter car model) [1]. For the given data and targeted value [1]: $L=80$ cm, $\delta_{\max}=7.6$ cm, and allowed height = 250 mm [3]. The cross section has a rectangular shape with filleted corners to avoid the effect of stresses concentration, particularly in the course of cornering of a vehicle. According to the approach of “Mohr-Circle”, the maximum induced stress in either of the three alternatives of springs, could be calculated as follows [8]:

σ_a (stress along the first constructional direction) = 0 (for no loads in the horizontal direction)

σ_b (stress along the second constructional direction) = σ_y direction

σ_c (stress along the third constructional direction) = 0 (for plane stress)

Therefore, the combined maximum stress (principle stress) σ_1 could be taken directly as the induced stress due to the normal applied force and the corresponding bending moment.

2.1 STEEL SEMI-ELLIPTIC MULTI-LEAF SPRINGS

Using the formulae of calculating the maximum deflection and the maximum induced stress of a steel semi-elliptic multi-leaf spring [6,7], the structural parameters of such spring could be calculated based on a given targeted value of the design as follows.

Fig. 1 Multi-leaf spring loaded by a force F

2.1.1 THEORETICAL DEFLECTION ANALYSIS OF STEEL SEMI-ELLIPTIC MULTI-LEAF SPRINGS

For the given data [1]: The allowable stress in a steel semi-elliptic multi-leaf spring could be taken as $\sigma_{\text{allowable}}=600$ MPa [7].

The thickness of one leaf (h) could be calculated as follows:

$$h = \left(\frac{1}{12}\right) \times 10^{-6} K_1 L^2 \left(\frac{\sigma_{\text{allowable}}}{\delta_{\max}}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{12}\right) \times 10^{-6} (1.25)(80)^2 \left(\frac{6000}{7.6}\right) = 0.53 \text{ cm}$$

Where: K_1 is the unequal length and friction factor (taken to be 1.25).

Hence, h could be taken as 0.6 cm.

The structural parameters could be calculated based on the maximum vertical deflection as follows [6,7].

$$\delta = \frac{K_1 FL^3}{4Enbh^3}$$

$$nb = 26.55$$

Where: n is the number of leaves & b is the width of the spring (cm)

For $n=5$, b could be taken as 6 cm.

2.1.2 THEORETICAL INDUCED STRESSES ANALYSIS OF STEEL SEMI-ELLIPTIC MULTI-LEAF SPRINGS

The maximum corresponding induced stress (σ) is 600 MPa, which could be confirmed using the following formula [6,7].

$$\sigma = \frac{3FL}{2nbh^2}$$

2.2 STEEL E-SPRINGS

2.2.1 THEORETICAL DEFLECTION ANALYSIS OF STEEL E-SPRINGS (USING CASTIGLIANO'S THEOREM)

The concept of superposition for strain energy could be applied to each portion of the E-spring. Each portion of the E-spring in Figs. 2-i & 2-ii could be analyzed as given next [8]

Fig. 2-i E-spring loaded by a compressive force F

2-ii Free-Body Diagram of E-spring loaded by a compressive force F

$$U_1 = \int_0^{176.2} \frac{\left(\frac{F}{\cos 8.42}\right)^2 dx}{2EI_1} + \int_0^{176.2} \frac{K\left(\frac{F}{\cos 8.42}\right)^2 dx}{2A_1G} = 932096 \frac{F^2}{EI_1} + 135.1 \frac{F^2}{A_1G}$$

$$U_2 = 2 \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{(FR_{mean} \sin \theta + FL)^2 d\theta}{2A_2Ee_2} + 2 \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{KV^2 R_{mean}^2 d\theta}{2A_2G} - 2 \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{NR_{mean}}{2A_2E} d\theta$$

Where: $K=1.5$ (for a rectangular cross section)

Hence,

$$U_2 = 41166 \frac{F^2}{A_2E} + 21 \frac{F^2}{A_2G} - 17.6 \frac{F}{A_2E}$$

$$U_3 = \int_0^{163.09} \frac{(F(x + 11.17))^2 dx}{2EI_1} + \int_0^{163.09} \frac{KF^2 dx}{2A_1G} = 881466 \frac{F^2}{EI_1} + 122.3 \frac{F^2}{A_1G}$$

$$U_4 = 2 \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{(Fr_{mean}(1 - \sin \theta))^2 d\theta}{2A_1Ee_1} + 2 \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{KV^2 r_{mean} d\theta}{2A_1G} - 2 \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{Nr_{mean}}{2A_1E} d\theta = 125 \frac{F^2}{A_1E} + 13.2 \frac{F^2}{A_1G} - 11.2 \frac{F}{A_1E}$$

Due to symmetry, portions 6, 10 and 14 are manipulated similarly as portions 2 in Fig. 2-ii. Also, portions 5, 7, 9, 11 and 13 are manipulated as portion 3, portions 8 and 12 are manipulated as portion 4, and portion 15 is manipulated as portion 1. Therefore, the total strain energy U becomes as given next.

$$U = 2U_1 + 4U_2 + 6U_3 + 3U_4$$

Accordingly, the overall vertical deflection of the steel E-spring becomes as follows.

$$\delta_y = \frac{\partial U}{\partial F} = 100.7 \text{ mm}$$

2.2.2 THEORITICAL INDUCED STRESSES ANALYSIS OF STEEL E-SPRINGS (USING "CURVED BEAM" APPROACH)

At the critical section "B" in Fig. 2-ii, the total induced stress could be calculated using the following formula [8].

$$\sigma = S - \frac{F}{A_2} = \frac{Mh_i}{A_2 e_2 R_i} - \frac{F}{A_2} = \frac{(5447)(200)(6.68)}{(15.88 \times 60)(1.274)(9.69)} - \frac{5447}{(15.88 \times 60)} = 613 \text{ MPa}$$

It should be noted, however, that the maximum bending stress always occurs at the inside fiber, because of the symmetrical cross section.

2.3 STEEL C-SPRINGS

2.3.1 THEORITICAL DEFLECTION ANALYSIS OF STEEL C-SPRINGS (USING CASTIGLIANO'S THEOREM)

The concept of superposition for strain energy could be applied to each portion of the C-spring. Each portion of the C-spring in Figs.

Fig. 3-i C-spring loaded by a compressive force Fig. 3-ii Free-Body Diagram of C-spring loaded by a compressive force F

$$U_1 = \int_0^{63.1} \frac{(Fx)^2 dx}{2EI_1} + \int_0^{63.1} \frac{KF^2 dx}{2A_1G} = 41873 \frac{r}{EI_1} + 47 \frac{r}{A_1G}$$

$$U_2 = 2 \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{(FR_{mean} \sin \theta + FL)^2 d\theta}{2A_2Ee_2} + 2 \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{KV^2 R_{mean} d\theta}{2A_2G} - 2 \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{NR_{mean}}{2A_2E} d\theta = 212153 \frac{F^2}{A_2E} + 153 \frac{F^2}{A_2G} - 130 \frac{F}{A_2E}$$

Due to symmetry, the horizontal portion 3 could be manipulated similarly as portion 1 in Fig. 3-ii. Therefore, the total strain energy U becomes as given next.

$$U = 2U_1 + U_2$$

Accordingly, the overall vertical deflection of the steel C-spring becomes as follows.

$$\delta_y = 13mm$$

2.3.2 THEORITICAL INDUCED STRESSES ANALYSIS OF STEEL C-SPRINGS (USING “CURVED BEAM” APPROACH)

At the critical section “B” in Fig. 3-ii, the total induced stress could be calculated using the following formula [8].

$$\sigma = S - \frac{F}{A_2} = \frac{Mh_i}{A_2 e_2 R_i} - \frac{F}{A_2} = \frac{(5447)(200)(7.78)}{(15.88 \times 60)(0.162)(121.83)} - \frac{5447}{(15.88 \times 60)} = 445MPa$$

It should be noted, however, that the maximum bending stress always occurs at the inside fiber, because of the symmetrical cross section.

2.4 DISCUSSION OF THE THEORITICAL RESULTS

Steel E-spring has showed a superior deflection capability (100.7mm) maintaining the maximum induced stress level (613MPa) nearly as that of steel semi-elliptic multi-leaf spring (600MPa). While steel C-spring has proved its advantage of relatively low level of maximum induced stress (445MPa), it showed a poor deflection capability (13mm). It could be concluded that steel E-spring could be considered as the best of them and its maximum induced stress level could be reduced considerably by reducing its maximum deflection to the targeted value of 76mm deflection. Moreover, such stride could result in more reduction in the space requirements for the steel E-spring which is an additional distinct advantage over the steel semi-elliptic multi-leaf spring.

3. NUMERICAL MODELS

In an endeavor to verify the comparison of the diversified configurations of steel springs, COSMOS/M package is used as a finite element tool to build and solve numerical models for them. Three finite element models are manipulated in this numerical analysis. The material type in these three models is steel AISI 9255 Alloy steel. These models are subjected to the same applied load of 555 kg, and of the same geometry as shown in Figs. 1, 2-i, and 3-i respectively. The element group for these models is taken as a TETRA4R 4-node tetrahedral with trans/rot DOF.

3.1 NUMERICAL RESULTS

3.1.1 STEEL SEMI-ELLIPTIC MULTI-LEAF SPRINGS

Figs. 4-i & 4-ii present the maximum vertical displacement Y of the deformed shape, maximum induced stress, and induced stresses distribution of the Steel semi-elliptic multi-leaf spring.

3.1.2 STEEL E-SPRINGS

Figs. 5-i & 5-ii present the maximum vertical displacement Y of the deformed shape, maximum induced stress, and induced stresses distribution of the steel E-spring.

3.1.3 STEEL C-SPRINGS

Figs. 6-i & 6-ii present the maximum vertical displacement Y of the deformed shape, maximum induced stress, and induced stresses distribution of the steel C-spring.

Fig. 4-ii Maximum induced stress & Induced stresses distribution in steel multi-leaf spring

Fig. 5-ii Maximum induced stress & Induced stresses distribution in steel E-spring

Fig. 6-ii Maximum induced stress & Induced stresses distribution in steel C-spring

Fig. 4-i Maximum vertical displacement & Deformed shape of steel multi leaf spring

Fig. 5-i Maximum vertical displacement & Deformed shape of steel E-spring

Fig. 6-i Maximum vertical displacement & Deformed shape of steel C-spring

3.2 DISCUSSION OF THE NUMERICAL RESULTS

Throughout the obtained results, it is apparent that the theoretical results agree well with the numerical results as shown in the summary of the theoretical and the numerical analyses in Table 1. It is noted that because of the symmetry in the geometry, load and boundary conditions of the two hinged joints of the E-spring as well as the C-spring, the numerical models of them are built based on a lower fixed joint and an upper movable hinged joint. Such a result leads to half of the total vertical displacement, since practically the two joints are movable and hinged. It is clear that the best of these three models is the E-spring because of its superior deflection capabilities and its reduced space requirements. Such superior deflection capability of the E-spring becomes an advantage to obtain a soft ride of vehicles, particularly if the spring rate stiffness of such a spring is nonlinear [6].

Table 1 Theoretical and numerical results of maximum overall vertical deflection & maximum induced stresses of diversified configurations of springs.

Type & Material of Spring	Maximum overall vertical deflection (mm)		Maximum induced stress (MPa)	
	Theoretical	Numerical	Theoretical	Numerical
Steel semi-elliptic multi-leaf spring	76	72	600	610.2
Steel E-spring	100.7	61x2 = 122	613	631
Steel C-spring	13	10x2 = 20	445	392

4. A PROPOSAL FOR THE OPTIMAL GEOMETRICAL ASPECT RATIOS OF THE E-SPRING

A global-search optimization technique (Genetic Algorithm technique) based on a random search optimization process, is used to optimize the geometrical aspect ratios of a steel E-spring as shown in Fig. 7. Such optimization approach is implemented through a mathematical modeling package called MATLAB 6.0. Firstly, an examination of multi-modal function is carried out for the objective function, to justify the implementation of Genetic Algorithm. Secondly, a Genetic Algorithm technique is applied to get the global optimal aspect ratios of the E-spring [16].

Fig. 7 Horizontal aspect ratio a'/b' and vertical aspect ratio a/b of E-spring

The overall vertical deflection of such spring could be considered as the objective function in such optimization approach. The equation of such vertical deflection could be calculated as follows (similar to E-spring of part 2.2.1).

$$\delta_y = \frac{\partial U}{\partial F} = \left(\frac{6F}{EI_1} \left(\frac{L_3^3}{3} + rL_3^2 + r^2L_3 \right) + \frac{9F}{A_1G} L_3 \right) + \left(\frac{2.4F}{A_1E \left(r - \frac{9.54}{r+4.77} \right)} r^2 + \frac{7.2F}{A_1G} r - \frac{3}{A_1E} r \right) + \left(\frac{0.73F}{EI_1} L_1^3 + \frac{3.28F}{A_1G} L_1 \right) + \left(\frac{8F}{A_2E \left(R - \frac{14.61}{R+7.3} \right)} (0.79R^2 + 1.99L_1R + 1.54L_1^2) + \frac{9.44F}{A_2G} R - \frac{4}{A_2E} R \right) \quad (1)$$

Where:

$$r = \frac{125}{6V+3} \quad \& \quad R = \frac{125}{6 + \left(\frac{3}{V}\right)} \quad \& \quad L_1 = 107.6 - \frac{130}{6 + \left(\frac{3}{V}\right)} \quad \& \quad L_3 = 110H - \frac{125}{6 + \left(\frac{3}{V}\right)} - \frac{125}{6V+3}$$

Where: H & V are the horizontal & vertical aspect ratios

$$H = \frac{a'}{b'} \quad \& \quad V = \frac{a}{b}$$

Subject to:

$$0.96 \leq V \leq 1.37$$

$$\frac{0.38(V + 1)}{(2V + 1)} \leq H \leq 1$$

(2)

4.1 MULTI-MODAL CONDITION

A multi-modal function is one that has more than one peak (maximum) or valley (minimum) in a given interval [13]. The modality of equation (1) could be examined in view of such concept using the so-called built-in function “FMINCON”, which is one of the built-in functions in MATLAB 6.0. In such built-in function, a local-search optimizer is run regarding equation (1) as the constrained objective function, and inequalities (2) as the constraints, starting search from a point of arbitrary values of the continuous design variables. Such check revealed that by altering the starting point of search, different values of local optima could be found. Therefore, equation (1) could be considered as a multi-modal objective function.

4.2 GENETIC ALGORITHM APPROACH

Genetic Algorithm (GA) is a global-search optimizer that can find the global optimum solution with a high probability [13]. Previous work pointed out the applicability of GA in layout optimization problems for shell structures made of unidirectional composite materials [15]. GAs are search algorithms which simulate the mechanics of natural genetics for artificial systems based on natural selection [16]. Natural selection, where the fittest individuals have the highest probability of survival, is the fundamental concept in this algorithm. An individual is coded by a string; in its turn the string can be formed of either one or a number of chromosomes. Each chromosome represents one optimizing variable. The fundamental advantage of the genetic algorithms lies in the non-differential relations; it means that the GA does not require gradient sensitivity analysis [15].

A genetic algorithm consists of three operations: function evaluation, selection, and reproduction, and the two main classes of genetic operations are mutation and crossover [16]. When considering a class of problems that have a relatively few number of parameters, as in the present work, the real coding has proved to be more efficient than the binary type [16]. The basic operators of natural genetics are reproduction, cross-over, and mutation. In the current work, a Tournament selection, Simple cross-over and Whole uniform mutation, are used. The Tournament selection has a procedure as follows.

- Selection of a chromosome using roulette-wheel selection for n times of repetition.
- The best chromosome among the n ones selected by roulette-wheel selection, could be used.

The Simple cross-over operator has a procedure as follows.

- For a randomly selected pair of chromosomes $x_1 = \{x_{11}, x_{12}, \dots, x_{1k}, \dots, x_{1n}\}$ and $x_2 = \{x_{21}, x_{22}, \dots, x_{2k}, \dots, x_{2n}\}$, a random location k in the chromosome is chosen.
- Chromosomes x_1, x_2 are replaced by chromosomes y_1, y_2 , where, $y_1 = \{x_{11}, x_{12}, \dots, x_{1k}, x_{2k+1}, \dots, x_{2n}\}$ and $y_2 = \{x_{21}, x_{22}, \dots, x_{2k}, x_{1k+1}, \dots, x_{1n}\}$.

The Whole uniform mutation operator has a procedure as follows.

- For a randomly selected chromosome $x = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k, \dots, x_n\}$, a random location k in the chromosome is chosen, where k is chosen between 1 and n.
- For each value of k, x_k is replaced with a random number between $[left_k, right_k]$, where left and right are the bounds on the variable x_k .

The number of generations in the present work is 5000, along with a population size of 50. The results of such optimization approach are represented through MATLAB 6.0 as shown in Figs. 8 & 9.

4.3 DISCUSSION OF OPTIMIZATION RESULTS

Figs. 8 & 9 have showed the best horizontal and vertical geometrical aspect ratios of the given E-spring. The best horizontal aspect ratio should be “1” for any value of the overall horizontal dimension as shown in Fig.7. The best vertical aspect ratio should be “1.37” for the given allowable vertical height of space (250mm) because of functional and manufacturing considerations as shown in Fig. 7 as well.

5. A PROPOSED OPTIMIZED LAMINATED FIBROUS COMPOSITE E-SPRING

Although the optimal geometrical aspect ratios of the E-spring in part 4 are based on the relations applied only for isotropic material, we could apply such resulting aspect ratios to the same E-spring but of composite material. Such stride could be applied since that optimal results are geometrical aspect ratios and not absolute values of deflection. Therefore, The resulting optimal laminated fibrous composite E-spring is shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10 Optimized Laminated Fibrous Composite E-spring

The special features of hybridization can be used advantageously in automobiles products. Gr-GI-Ep fiber combination composites have numerous benefits as reduced net section thickness compared with all glass, lower costs than all-advanced composite, and surface-crack stopping [10]. Graphite fibers exhibit excellent resistance to creep, excellent resistance to fatigue loading, and superior damping characteristics. Such damping characteristics could modify suspension characteristics that may result

in a considerable cost saving by using lower duty dampers. E-glass fibers exhibit a considerably low level of acoustic stress, high strength, in addition to their low cost. Epoxy systems are superior to polyester particularly with regard to adhesion with a wide variety of fibers, moisture resistance, and chemical resistance [10,12]. Therefore, a hybrid laminate of composite materials of Graphite, E-glass and Epoxy, is used in such optimized laminated fibrous composite E-spring.

The E-spring in Fig. 10, is composed of portions of nominal thickness (i.e. 9.54mm), as portions 1,3,4,5,7,8,9,11,12,13,15, as shown in Fig. 2-ii, and of portions of intensified thickness (i.e. 14.62mm), as portions 2,6,10,14. The effective laminate properties of such portions could be calculated as follows.

5.1 EFFECTIVE LAMINATE PROPERTIES OF THE PORTIONS OF NOMINAL THICKNESS (i.e. 9.54 mm)

The following constructional data are applied:

Hybrid-composite (Continuous E-glass fibers reinforcement & Chopped graphite fibers reinforcement)

Ply thickness = 0.635mm

Fiber volume fraction = 60% (typical fiber volume fraction) [6]

Laminate anatomy is as follows:

40% Elastomer-toughened Epoxy, 51.5% E-glass roving, and 8.5% Graphite, PAN, lower-cost high strength (LHS), AS-4 fibers.

Laminate stacking sequence is as follows [6]:

$[0_{Gr,Chop} / 0_{E-gl} / 45_{E-gl} / 0_{E-gl} / 0_{E-gl} / -45_{E-gl} / 90_{E-gl} / 0_{E-gl}]_S$

5.1.1 CHOPPED GRAPHITE/EPOXY LAMINA

Chopped Graphite/Epoxy lamina could be analyzed using modified Cox model with the following values:

$d = 0.010\text{mm}$ (typical fiber diameter) [9]

A_f (cross-sectional area of the fiber) = $\pi (d/2)^2 = 8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^2$

D (outside diameter of a Representative Volume Element) = 0.0154 mm

e (distance between fiber ends in modified Cox model) = 0.25 (d) = 0.0025 mm [9]

Therefore, the critical fiber length L_c could be calculated as follows [9].

$$L_c = \frac{dS f_1}{2\tau_y} = \frac{(0.010)(2896)}{2(20)} = 0.72\text{mm}$$

We could take the discontinuous Graphite fiber length as 0.8mm, to make the lamina behavior nearly as that of continuous-fiber-reinforced lamina [10,12].

Consequently, using the classical lamination theory, the effective extensional stiffness matrix of the laminate of the portions of 9.54 mm thickness could be as follows [6,9,12].

$$A_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 4.1645 & 0.8875 & 0 \\ 0.8875 & 2.3189 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.5175 \end{bmatrix} \times 10^5 \text{ MPa}$$

Therefore, The effective laminate properties of the portions of 9.54mm thickness are as follows.

$$E_{x_C} = \frac{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2}{(A_{22})(9.54)} = 4.01 \times 10^4 \text{ MPa} \ \& \ E_{y_C} = \frac{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2}{(A_{11})(9.54)} = 2.23 \times 10^4 \text{ MPa} \ \&$$

$$\nu_{xy} = \frac{A_{12}}{A_{22}} = 0.38 \ \& \ \nu_{yx} = \frac{A_{12}}{A_{11}} = 0.21 \ \& \ G_{xy_C} = \frac{A_{66}}{9.54} = 5.42 \times 10^3 \text{ MPa}$$

Where: E_{x_C} & E_{y_C} are the effective laminate elastic moduli along the structural axes x & y

ν_{x_C} & ν_{y_C} are the effective laminate Poisson's ratios along the structural axes x & y

G_{xy_C} is the effective laminate shear modulus in the structural xy plane

5.2 EFFECTIVE LAMINATE PROPERTIES OF THE PORTIONS OF INTENSIFIED THICKNESS (i.e. 14.61 mm)

The following constructional data are applied:

Hybrid-composite (Continuous E-glass fibers reinforcement & Chopped graphite fibers reinforcement & Chopped E-glass fibers reinforcement)

Ply thickness = 0.635mm

Fiber volume fraction = 60% (typical fiber volume fraction) [6]

Laminate anatomy is as follows:

40% Elastomer-toughened Epoxy, 54.5% E-glass roving, and 5.5% Graphite, PAN, lower-cost high strength (LHS), AS-4 fibers.

Laminate stacking sequence is as follows [6]:

[0_{E-gl,Chop} /0_{E-gl,Chop} /0_{E-gl,Chop} /0_{E-gl,Chop} /0_{Gr,Chop} /0_{E-gl} /45_{E-gl} /0_{E-gl} /0_{E-gl} /-45_{E-gl} /90_{E-gl} /0_{E-gl}]_s

5.2.1 CHOPPED E-GLASS/EPOXY LAMINA

Chopped E-glass/Epoxy lamina could be analyzed using modified Cox model with the following values:

$d = 0.076\text{mm}$ (typical fiber diameter) [6]

$A_f = \pi (d/2)^2 = 0.0045 \text{ mm}^2$

$D = 0.106 \text{ mm}$

$e = 0.019 \text{ mm}$ [9]

Therefore, the critical fiber length L_c could be calculated as follows [6,9,12].

$$L_c = \frac{dS_{f1}}{2\tau_y} = \frac{(0.076)(1700)}{2(20)} = 3.23\text{mm}$$

We could take the discontinuous E-glass fiber length as 3.3mm, to make the lamina behavior nearly as that of continuous-fiber-reinforced lamina [10,12].

Consequently, using the classical lamination theory, the effective extensional stiffness matrix of the laminate of the portions of 14.61 mm thickness could be as follows [9].

$$A_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 6.2401 & 1.1335 & 0 \\ 1.1335 & 3.0876 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.6586 \end{bmatrix} \times 10^5 \text{ MPa}$$

Therefore, The effective laminate properties of the portions of 14.61mm thickness are as follows.

$$E_{x_C} = \frac{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2}{(A_{22})(14.61)} = 3.98 \times 10^4 \text{ MPa} \ \& \ E_{y_C} = \frac{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2}{(A_{11})(14.61)} = 1.97 \times 10^4 \text{ MPa} \ \&$$

$$v_{xy} = \frac{A_{12}}{A_{22}} = 0.37 \ \& \ v_{yx} = \frac{A_{12}}{A_{11}} = 0.18 \ \& \ G_{xy_C} = \frac{A_{66}}{14.61} = 4.51 \times 10^3 \text{ MPa}$$

5.3 NUMEERICAL ANALYSIS OF OPTIMIZED LAMINATED FIBROUS COMPOSITE E-SPRING

COSMOS/M package is used as a finite element tool to build and solve the numerical model for the optimized laminated fibrous composite E-spring. The material type in this model is the material of the effective laminate properties in each portion of E-spring. This model is subjected to the same applied load of 555 kg (Quarter car model), and has geometry as shown in Fig. 10. The element group for this model is taken as a TETRA4R 4-node tetrahedral with trans/rot DOF.

Fig 11-4 Maximum vertical displacement & Deformed shape of Optimized Laminated Fibrous Composite E-spring

Fig 11-5 Maximum induced stress & Induced stresses distribution in an optimized laminated fibrous composite E-spring

The numerical results have revealed that the maximum deflection of the optimized laminated fibrous composite E-spring is 78mm, and the maximum induced stress is 382MPa, which agree with the targeted value of deflection in addition to a considerably reduced induced stress in comparison with the maximum induced stress in the composite leaf spring (534 MPa) [1]. Consequently, the spring stiffness of the shown dimensions of laminated composite E-spring subjected to static loading is investigated numerically with a result of 7.2 kg/mm. Furthermore, because of its construction, a stiffening-up of the spring will occur as deflection increases: this is called a progressive or variable-rate spring [4]. The volume saving of the optimized laminated fibrous composite E-spring in comparison with the steel multi leaf spring is 65%. In the evaluation of the overall performance of a suspension system, the following two aspects should be considered: vibration isolation, and road holding. It could be concluded that a lighter un-sprung mass, and a softer suspension spring will generally provide better overall vibration isolation and improved road-holding in the low-to-mid frequency range [11]. Therefore, the optimized laminated fibrous composite E-spring could provide better vibration isolation, and road holding than the traditional springs. Future work shall investigate the spring rate of the laminated fibrous composite E-spring subjected to dynamic loading.

6. CONCLUSION

In this research work, some leaf springs of diversified configurations are studied. The study shows that E-spring could be the best of them regarding the induced stresses and resulted displacements. The optimal geometrical parameters of the E-spring could be obtained numerically to be as “1” for the horizontal aspect ratio, and “1.37” for the vertical aspect ratio. The static stiffness of such spring is investigated numerically giving a result of 7.2 kg/mm. The volume saving of composite E-spring is 65% in comparison with the steel multi-leaf spring.

REFERENCES

1. Sancaktar, E., Gratton, M., Design, Analysis, and Optimization of Composite Leaf Springs for Light Vehicle Applications, Elsevier Science Ltd., S0263-8223(98)00136-6, (1999).
2. Sardou, M.A., and Patricia, D., Light and Low Cost Composite Compression C-springs for Vehicle Suspension, SAE, 2000-01-0100, (2000).
3. Azzam, B.S.N., Mokhtar, M.O.A., and Naga, S.A.R., Theoretical and Numerical Analysis of Fibrous Composite C-springs, SAE, 2001-01-2710, (2001).
4. Hillier, V.A.W., Fundamentals of Motor Vehicle Technology, Stanley Thornes, 1991, pp.357-360.
5. Mott, R.L., Machine Elements in Mechanical Design, Macmillan Publishing Company, 1992, Appendix 3.
6. Rothbart, H.A., Mechanical Design Handbook, McGraw-Hill, 1996, p.15.3, 15.8, 15.10, 15.12, 28.23, 28.24.
7. Metwalli, S.M., Machine Design Fundamentals, Cairo University, 1990, pp.109-121.
8. Beer, F.P., Johnston, E.R., Mechanics of Materials, McGraw-Hill, 1992, pp.257-268, 367-369, 610-615.
9. Gibson, R.F., Principles of Composite Material Mechanics, McGraw Hill, 1994, p.18, 157, 161, 168, 169, 274, 326, 330.
10. Schwartz, M.M., Composite Materials Handbook, McGraw-Hill, 1992, p.1.12, 2.79, 2.95, 2.120, 2.123, 2.127, 3.71, 4.21, 8.27, 8.29.
11. Wong, J. Y., Theory of Ground Vehicles, John Wiley, 1993, p.303, 348, 353, 355, 357, 358, 360, 365.
12. Agarwal, B.D., Broutman, L.J., Analysis and Performance of Fiber Composites, John Wiley, 1990, p.7, 124, 164, 192, 198, 241.
13. Rao, S.S., Engineering Optimization, John Wiley, 1999, pp.65-69, 808.
14. Sato, N., Kurauchi, T., Kamigaito, O., Material Improvement and Quality Assurance for Composite Leaf Springs Based on Micro-fracture Mechanism, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 26, No. 9/1992, (1992).
15. Muc, A., Gurba, W., Genetic Algorithms and Finite Element Analysis in Optimization of Composite Structures, Elsevier Science Ltd., S0263-8223(01)00098-8, (2001).
16. Tabakov, P.Y., Multidimensional Design Optimization of Laminated Structures Using an Improved Genetic Algorithm, Elsevier Science Ltd., S0263-8223(01)00109-X, (2001).